
bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for
innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of marine and coastal geohazard

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Toolkit for Virtual Reality exploration in under water environments

BridgET Project Result 05

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BridgET: Bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of climate change-induced marine and coastal geohazard

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PROJECT RESULT REPORT

05 - Toolkit for virtual reality exploration of underwater environments

Introduction

This project result consists of an integrated toolkit designed to support virtual reality (VR) exploration of underwater geological landscapes, with a focus on the Santorini Volcanic Complex. It combines a webbased interactive platform and a supporting report that documents the development process and the scientific background of the featured sites.

The resource was developed following fieldwork campaigns involving ROV-based imagery collection by researchers with expertise in marine geology and underwater photogrammetry. The gathered images and videos were then processed and curated to create a fully interactive, multimedia-based VR toolkit, freely available online at:

⇒ <https://arcg.is/1DSeTeo>

The Story Map platform features a guided tour through a selection of key underwater and coastal locations, using 360° videos, photographs, interactive maps, and 3D models. Users can explore features such as dyke swarms, shipwrecks, volcanic craters, and lava flows by navigating the interface, interacting with the content, and learning through short, accessible geological explanations.

The accompanying PDF report outlines the development methodology and scientific relevance of the featured sites, and serves as a resource for instructors and students engaging in virtual exploration activities.

This VR toolkit is:

- Freely accessible to students, educators, and the public
- Designed for use in university teaching, particularly in marine geology, volcanology, and science communication
- Based on real scientific field data collected using ROV systems
- Intended to be expanded in the future through additional case studies and educational resources

The toolkit has already been used in classroom and outreach contexts and represents a powerful tool for blending scientific research, digital innovation, and experiential learning.

List of Deliverables:

Deliverable 5.1: Toolkit for virtual reality exploration of underwater environments: a story map at <https://arcg.is/1DSeTeo>

Deliverable 5.2: Report on developed methodology

1. Project Result 05 – Deliverable overview

Below is a description of the deliverable produced as part of project result “Toolkit for virtual reality exploration of underwater environments”.

Deliverable 5.1 – Toolkit for virtual reality exploration of underwater environments

Description: An integrated VR toolkit consisting of a web-based Story Map. The resource presents underwater and coastal geological sites using 360° videos, maps, and 3D models, based on ROV-acquired data. It is designed for immersive education and science communication, and is freely accessible online.

Type of Output: Web-based Interactive Resource

Language: English

Access/Format: Online Platform

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: <https://arcg.is/1DSeTeo>

Deliverable 5.2 – Technical report

Description: A supporting PDF report with the description of the integrated VR toolkit consisting of a web-based Story Map.

Type of Output: Technical report

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF document

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: Santorini's Toolkit for Virtual Reality Exploration.pdf

Deliverable 5.1

Toolkit for virtual reality exploration of underwater environments

[🔗 https://arcg.is/1DSeTeo](https://arcg.is/1DSeTeo)

Deliverable 5.2

Santorini's Toolkit for Virtual Reality Exploration

This interactive application will guide you through captivating locations in the Santorini Volcanic Complex. Begin with the **map tour** to get an overview of all locations before diving into a detailed 3D exploration of a selected site.

The map tour is designed to provide an immersive experience through a combination of photos, videos, 360-degree videos, and interactive maps, offering insights into the unique features and geological significance of each site. You can scroll down to view all locations in sequence or if you want to explore the available material for a specific site, select its location on the map.

1 - Dyke swarm

Between 530 and 430 ka (and possibly more recently), lava emissions led to the formation of a small stratovolcano in northern Santorini. The remnants of this volcano, known as Peristeria, have been extensively cut by numerous dykes, which once supplied magma to surface eruptions. Many of these dykes exhibit columnar jointing perpendicular to their sides. They are predominantly aligned NNE-SSW, following the orientation of the regional rift zone that Santorini lies within. The dykes belong to two distinct ages: some fed Peristeria-age lavas, while others supplied magma to the Skaros lava flows (67–54 ka) that overlie Peristeria. Notably, this dyke swarm contains some of the most primitive basalts found on Santorini.

The 360-degree video reveals an underwater section of this dyke swarm, offering an immersive view of its geological features. The photo captures the onshore cliffs of the region.

2 – Skaros

The Skaros lava shield formed between 67 and 54 ka, filling and eventually overflowing a pre-existing caldera. At its peak development, it reached 350 meters above present-day sea level. However, the shield was partially destroyed during the caldera collapse triggered by the 22 ka Cape Riva eruption. Composed of basaltic and andesitic lava flows, the shield contains interlayered orange tuffs and soils oxidized by heat. Its formation ultimately concluded with a major andesitic explosive eruption. The image shows the onshore vertical cliffs of Skaros Shield, which are composed of multiple basaltic to andesitic lava flows.

3 - Pagkos volcanic crater

The crater lies atop a submarine cone at 40m b.s.l. in between Nea Kameni and Fira port. It has a diameter of 10m and is covered by soft sediments. Its cone slopes are very abrupt and composed of dacitic lavas, while some parts of it are experiencing ongoing degassing. The video captured with an ROV, shows soft sediments covering the volcanic cone.

4 - May islands

The video captured with the ROV, reveals the offshore May islands which sunk during the 1866 eruption of Nea Kameni.

5 - Modern shipwreck

It was a steamship that sank in 1926 due to a fire in the engine room. The ship lies between Nea and Palaia Kameni right next to the famous hot springs. Over the years, the ship's hull has blended into the environment, creating a type of artificial reef, where various marine species of the area can be found. With the 360-degree video, you can navigate alongside the diver as they explore the shipwreck, offering an immersive experience where viewers can look around freely and feel as if they are diving themselves. This allows for a realistic underwater adventure, showcasing the wreck from different angles and perspectives. By moving the screen with your mouse, you can follow the diver's path, observe marine life, and explore the details of the submerged vessel as if you were there in person.

6 - Thirassia steps

Andesitic lava forming characteristics geometrical columns. The multimedia content, including photo and video, offers an immersive and detailed view of the area.

7 - Modern shipwreck Oia

The Oia Wreck is the remains of a cargo ship named AVLIS MV, which was 75 meters long, had a 1,157 GRT tonnage, and was built in 1949. The vessel was originally owned by Xanthopoulos & Co. until 1970 when Chalkis Cement Co purchased it. On April 6, 1972, during a ballast voyage from Halkis to Santorini, AVLIS MV ran aground and wrecked off the coast of Santorini Island. Today, the only visible part of the vessel is its stern, which lies at a depth of 3 to 20 meters, making it easily accessible for both snorkelers and divers. The provided photos highlight various aspects of the shipwreck, showcasing its structure and details despite its prolonged submersion in water. As you completed the map tour, you've gained a wide-angle perspective of the various locations and their unique stories.

You can further explore one of these sites through a detailed 3D model. This model provides an interactive and in-depth exploration, allowing you to examine finer details and enhance your understanding of this particular location.

Thirassia steps 3D model

Press the play button to load the model. Use the mouse scroll wheel to adjust the zoom level and the left mouse button to rotate and tilt the view for a detailed exploration.

Virtual exploration allows us to uncover hidden details and experience landscapes from new perspectives. Continue your journey by exploring similar sites through additional virtual resources and interactive tools.

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